

higher with 30 kg N/ha than in the no-N check, 60 kg N gave significantly better yields than 30 kg, and 90 kg N

produced better IR42 yields than 60 kg N. IR36 yield at 90 kg N was not significantly higher than at 60 kg.

Applying 150 kg N did not significantly increase yield of either variety (see table).[§]

Ratoon crop performance of three rices

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Rice in Bangalore, Kolar, and Tumkur Districts of Karnataka, India, often is planted late because irrigation tanks have not filled, and can suffer cold damage. Land often remains fallow until wet season begins in Jun-Jul. We sought to determine the potential of a ratoon crop of rice planted in late wet season.

Mangala, CT1351, and Halubbalu were planted in 3.0- × 1.8-m plots in 4 replications on 15 Aug, 15 Sep, and 15 Oct in late kharif 1983-84.

Recommended practices were followed for the main crop, which was somewhat damaged by blast (BI) and low temperatures. The BI-damaged plots grew new tillers and produced some grain. The plots were ratooned after main season harvest. The ratoon crop was irrigated 2-3 times a month and was not cultivated or fertilized.

Halubbalu produced no grain in the main crop because of BI. Mangala and CT1351 yielded 1.5 to 2.5 t/ha and had moderate BI resistance. Ratoon yields are in the table. Mangala planted on 15

Ratoon yield of three rice varieties as influenced by three planting dates, Bangalore, India.^a

Variety		Planting date		
		15 Aug	15 Sep	15 Oct
Mangala	GY (t/ha)	1.81	1.41	1.21
	MCD (d)	118	126	130
	RCD (d)	85	90	80
CT1351	GY (t/ha)	0.94	1.07	1.25
	MCD (d)	127	134	140
	RCD (d)	100	110	100
Halubbalu (S317)	GY (t/ha)	0.93	1.49	1.55
	MCD (d)	136	138	148
	RCD (d)	105	116	110

^aGy = grain yield, MCD = main crop duration, RCD = ratoon crop duration.

Aug and ratooned in November yielded highest followed by Haiubbalu planted 15 Oct, and Mangala and Halubbalu planted 15 Sep. Yield data for the

ratoon crop are unreliable because there was considerable bird damage; however, they encourage further study of rice ratooning for the area.[§]

Regulating K⁺ and Na⁺ in two rice varieties grown in sodic soils

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Rice varieties differ in salt tolerance. Tolerant varieties generally have comparatively low Na⁺ content per unit dry weight with less imbalance in shoot K⁺. The ability to regulate those ions in leaves may help prevent Na⁺ excess in young plant parts. Damodar and Jaya, which have different salt tolerance, were grown under sodic conditions to study their ability to control K⁺ and Na⁺ contents in different laminae and their sheaths.

Forty-day-old seedlings were transplanted in pots with 8.5 kg sodic

soil of pH 9.5 and 9.8. Exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) was 52 and 69. Pots with normal soil (pH 8.1 and ESP 7) were the control. Soil was 41.4% sand, 35.0% silt, and 23.2% clay. Cation exchange capacity was 10.6 meq/100g.

Soil had 24, 11, and 85 mg/kg available NPK. One gram urea and 0.09 g ZnSO₄/pot were applied basally. An additional dose of 0.5 g urea/pot was applied at tillering and flowering.

After 45 d of growth, 3 sets of the top 4 fully expanded laminae were sampled and analyzed for K⁺ and Na⁺.

Differences in Na⁺ content were statistically significant and were in order 1 < 2 < 3 < 4. K⁺ was lowest in the first lamina of control plants. Each lamina of Damodar had significantly higher K⁺ than the corresponding one in Jaya; the reverse was true for Na⁺ (see figure).

Effect of sodicity on K⁺ and Na⁺ contents of different laminae of two rices, Haryana, India. Bars = 1st to 4th laminae K⁺, vertical lines = Na⁺.

Damodar is more salt tolerant than Jaya and regulated Na⁺ and K⁺ better. For example, at pH 9.8, Damodar had maximum increase of Na⁺ (1600%) in the 4th lamina as compared to Jaya's 1178% over the respective controls.

K⁺ content of each Damodar lamina decreased less than in Jaya. Reduction in the first lamina over the respective controls was 43% for Damodar and 51% for Jaya. Thus, each part of Damodar had lower Na⁺ to K⁺ ratio than that of Jaya.

Analysis 60 d after transplanting showed that each leaf sheath had higher Na⁺ content than its lamina in both genotypes (see table). The same was true for K⁺ for the first and second leaf

Effect of sodicity on Na⁺ content of first to fourth laminae (1 L to 4 L) and their sheaths (1 LS to 4 LS) in two rices (% dry weight), Haryana, India.

pH, ESP	Variety	Na ⁺ content									
		1 L	2 L	3 L	4 L	Mean	1 LS	2 LS	3 LS	4 LS	Mean
8.2	Damodar	0.087	0.070	0.077	0.077	0.078	0.413	0.427	0.473	0.463	0.444
	Jaya	0.093	0.126	0.123	0.143	0.121	0.303	0.410	0.677	0.917	0.577
9.5	Damodar	0.650	0.760	0.903	1.10	0.854	1.21	1.53	1.86	2.12	1.68
	Jaya	0.660	0.737	0.977	1.09	0.867	1.45	1.74	1.92	2.37	1.87
Mean		0.373	0.424	0.520	0.605		0.846	1.029	1.232	1.470	
CD at 5%		S × V × L 0.023					S × V × LS 0.045				

sheaths at pH 8.1. At pH 9.5, however, each lamina had higher K⁺ than its sheath. In both varieties, sodicity decreased K⁺ content and increased Na⁺.

Higher Na⁺ in older laminae seems to

occur because of its poor retranslocation from older to younger parts. K⁺ depletion was highest in older plant parts, suggesting that export of K⁺ from older to younger parts exceeded its import under stress. *S*

Nitrogen use efficiency in relation to seedling age and transplanting time

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We studied N use efficiency in terms of grain yield and N recovery in relation to seedling age at transplanting at PAU RRS. The 1981 and 1982 trials were in a split-plot design with 3 transplanting dates (30 Jun, 20 Jul, 9 Aug) and 5 N levels (0, 60, 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha) as main plots and 3 seedling ages at transplanting (30, 45, and 60 d) as subplots.

PK was applied at 13-25 kg/ha at last puddling. Urea N was applied in equal splits at transplanting, tillering, and panicle initiation. N recovery (kg grain/kg of applied N) was calculated:

$$\text{N recovery} = \frac{\text{Grain yield (kg/ha) in N plots} - \text{Grain yield (kg/ha) in 0 N control}}{\text{N level (kg/ha)}}$$

Transplanting 60-d-old seedlings gave highest grain yield (see figure). The differences in grain yield were most significant at later planting dates. Sixty-day-old seedlings outyielded 30 and 45-d-old seedlings with much higher differences under 0 N as well as under all other N levels with a margin of 0.58-1.1 and 0.184.48 t/ha.

Effect of transplanting schedule, N level, and seedling age on rice grain yield, Kapurthala, India.

Recovery increased with N application. Late-transplanted, 60-d seedlings had much higher N recovery than 30- and 45-d seedlings, although N recovery tended to remain at par for seedlings transplanted 30 Jun and 20 Jul.

The increase in grain yield and N recovery with older seedlings was the net result of balanced dry matter production, early flowering, and high spikelet fertility. *S*

Herbicides reduce azolla growth

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When azolla is inoculated in transplanted rice fields to fix N, it also competes with weeds by rapidly covering the water surface. However, it does not control all weeds. We studied